

Topological indices of Derived graphs of Bull Graph

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Abstract: A topological index is a numeric number that helps to find the characteristics of compounds. There are many applications of graph theory. In this paper we compute first and second Zagreb indices, Randić index, sum-connectivity index, harmonic index, inverse sum index, modified first and second Zagreb indices and first and second hyper Zagreb indices of the Splitting graph of Bull graph.

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Introduction

Mathematical objects have been used to represent the structure of a chemical compound. One such representation is that each atom is described by vertices and the bond between atoms is described by an edge. With this, mathematical tools can now be used to analyze the properties of chemical compounds that may be related to its structure. A mathematical formula that represents chemical species which have made a variety of methods of chemical structure is called the topological indices [11]. Topological indices are helpful when interpreting chemical constitution into numerical values which can be used for correlation with physical properties in quantitative structure property/activity relationship (QSPR/QSAR) studies. Quantitative structure-property relationship (QSPR) mathematical modeling method connects physical or chemical properties with a structure of a molecule [1]. Meanwhile, Quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) is a mathematical modeling method that show relationships between biological activities and the structural properties of chemical compounds [8]. We have here some studies of topological indices in QSPR/QSAR. Shanmukha, et. al used 13 degree based topological indices to study anticancer drugs in terms of QSPR [12]. Hosamani studied the QSPR of phytochemicals screened against SARS-CoV-2 3CLpro with the help of several topological indices [5]. In general, a topological index, also known as a graph-theoretic index, is a numerical invariant of a chemical graph. Harary index, Balaban index, molecular topological index, Wiener index, Hyper-Wiener index, and Zagreb indices are some of the well-studied topological indices. Topological indices are used to represent each chemical structure with a numerical value. These values are used to model different physicochemical properties and biological activities of chemical compounds [10]. The first topological index was introduced by Harry Wiener in 1947. He computed the sum of the distances of the shortest path between all pairs of vertices of a graph called Wiener index [13]. The

concept of the Wiener index was generalized by Milan Randić in 1993. It was the extension for all connected graphs and called it Hyper-Wiener index [9]. A variety of topological indices have been studied. In particular, the Balaban index, also called J index was developed by Balaban [2]. De first derived explicit expression of reformulated first Zagreb index of generalized hierarchical product of two connected graphs [3]. Gao et. al developed some degree-based topological indices of networks derived from Honey comb networks [4]. Recently, Mondal et. al obtained some of the topological properties of some chemical structures used to inhibit the outbreak and transmission of COVID-19 in terms of some degree-based and some neighborhood degree sum-based indices [10].

2. Preliminary concepts

Let G be a simple graph, with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The degree $d_g(u)$ of a vertex u is the number of edges that are incident to it. Since 1947 many number of topological indices have been found. One of the oldest and well known topological indices is the first and second Zagreb indices, was first introduced by Gutman et al. in 1972 [3], and it is defined as

$$M_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} d_g(u) + d_g(v)$$
$$M_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} d_g(u)d_g(v)$$

and The connectivity index introduced in 1975 by Milan Randić [4], is defined as

$$R(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d_g(u)d_g(v)}}$$

Recently, another variant of the Randić connectivity index called the sum-connectivity index $\chi(G)$ was introduced by B. Zhou and N. Trinajstić [5] in 2008. It is defined as

$$\chi(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{d_g(u) + d_g(v)}$$

In 2014 Jianxi Li and Chee Shiu introduced a new variant of the Randić index named the Harmonic

index which first appeared in [6] called the harmonic index $H(G)$ is defined as

$$H(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{2}{d_g(u) + d_g(v)}$$

Discrete Adriatic indices have been defined by Vukičević and Gašperov in 2010. One among such indices is the inverse sum indeg index, [7] and is defined as

$$ISI(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{d_g(u)d_g(v)}{d_g(u) + d_g(v)}$$

A. Milicevi, S. Nikoli, N. Trinajstić, introduced in 2004 the modified first and second Zagreb indices [8], and are respectively defined as

$$mM_1(G) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} \frac{1}{(d_g(u))^2}$$

$$mM_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{d_g(u)d_g(v)}$$

In 2013, Shirdel et al. introduced the first hyperZagreb index of a graph G , which is defined as

$$H_{M1}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_g(u) + d_g(v))^2$$

The second hyper-Zagreb index of a graph G is defined as

$$H_{M2}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_g(u)d_g(v))^2$$

Definition 2.1: The Bull Graph is a planar undirected graph with 5 vertices and 5 edges, in the form of a triangle with two disjoint pendant edges (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Bull graph

Definition 2.2: The middle graph $M(G)$ of a graph G is the graph whose vertex set is $V(G) \cup E(G)$ and in which two vertices are adjacent if and only if either they are adjacent edges of G or one is a vertex of G and other is an edge incident on it.

Figure 2: Middle graph of Bull graph

Definition 2.3: The total graph $T(G)$ of a graph G is the graph whose vertex set is $V(G) \cup E(G)$ and two vertices are adjacent whenever they are either adjacent or incident in G .

Figure 3 –Total graph of Bull graph

Definition 2.3: The Splitting graph $S(G)$ of graph G is the graph where for each vertex v of a graph G , take a new vertex v' and join v' to all points of G adjacent to v .

Figure 4 –splitting graph of Bull graph

Definition 2.4: The Shadow Graph $D_2(G)$ of a connected graph G is constructed by taking two copies of G , say G' and G . Join each vertex u' in G' to the neighbors of the corresponding vertex u'' in G'' .

Figure 5 –shadow graph of Bull graph

3.Main Results

In this paper we compute topological indices of some derived graphs of bull graph.

Theorem 3.1: If $S(B)$ is the splitting graph of Bull graph, then

- (i). $M_1(S(B)) = 115$. (ii). $M_2(S(B)) = 186$.
- (iii). $mM_1(S(B)) = 115$.
- (iv). $mM_2(S(B)) = 115$. (v). $HM_1(S(B)) = 983$.
- (vi). $HM_2(S(B)) = 115$.
- (vii). $R(S(B)) = 4.00311$ (viii). $\chi(S(B)) = 1.776$
- (ix) $ISI(S(B)) = 22.9428$.
- (X). $ABC(S(B)) = 2.84072$ (iX) $GAI(S(G)) = 6.33415$
- (X) $SO(S(B)) = 73.976$.

Proof: In $S(B)$, there are four pairs of edges with degrees 2,6 ; two pairs of edges with degrees 6,3 and one pair of edge with degrees 2,3 and 6,6.

With these degree sequences, we have

$$(i). M_1(S(B)) = \sum_{uv \in E(g)} d(u) + d(v)$$

$$= 4(2+6)+2(6+4)+2(6+1)+2(4+3)+2(6+3)+(2+3)+6+4 = 115$$

$$(ii). M_2(S(B)) = \sum_{uv \in E(g)} d(u)d(v)$$

$$= 4(2 \times 6)+2(6 \times 4)+2(6 \times 1)+2(4 \times 3)+2(6 \times 3)+(2 \times 3)+6 \times 4 = 186$$

$$(iii). mM_1(S(B)) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} \frac{1}{d(u)^2}$$

Here there are three vertices of degree 2, two vertices of degree 4, two vertices of degree 1,3 and one vertex of degree 4. Thus

$$mM_1(S(B)) = 3.1597$$

$$(iv). mM_2(S(B)) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{d(u)d(v)}$$

$$= \frac{4}{2.6} + \frac{2}{6.4} + \frac{2}{1.6} + \frac{2}{4.3} + \frac{2}{6.1} + \frac{1}{2.3} + \frac{1}{6.6} = 1.414$$

$$(v). HM_1(S(B)) = \sum_{uv \in E(g)} (d(u) + d(v))^2$$

$$= 4.(2+6)^2 + 2(6+4)^2 + 2(6+1)^2 + 2(4+3)^2 + 2(6+3)^2 + (2+3)^2 + (6+6)^2 = 983$$

$$(vi). HM_2(S(B)) = \sum_{uv \in E(g)} (d(u)d(v))^2$$

$$= 4.(2.6)^2 + 2(6.4)^2 + 2(6.1)^2 + 2(4.3)^2 + 2(6.3)^2 + (2.3)^2 + (6.6)^2 = 3808$$

$$(vii). R(S(B)) = \sum_{uv \in E(g)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d(u)d(v)}}$$

$$= \frac{4}{\sqrt{2.6}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{4.6}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{1.6}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{4.3}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{3.6}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2.3}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{6.6}} = 4.00311$$

$$(viii). \chi(S(B)) = \sum_{uv \in E(g)} \frac{1}{d(u)+d(v)} = 4.00311$$

$$(ix). ISI(S(B)) = \sum_{uv \in E(g)} \frac{d(u)d(v)}{d(u)+d(v)} = 22.9428$$

$$(x). ABC(S(B)) = \sum_{uv \in E(g)} \frac{\sqrt{d(u)d(v)-2}}{d(u)d(v)} = 2.84072$$

$$(xi). GAI(S(B)) = \sum_{uv \in E(g)} \frac{\sqrt{d(u)d(v)}}{d(u)+d(v)} = 6.33415$$

$$(xii). SO(S(B)) = \sum_{uv \in E(g)} \sqrt{d(u)^2 + d(v)^2} = 3.976$$

Theorem 3.2: If $M(B)$ is the middle graph of Bull graph, then

- (i). $M_1(M(B)) = 130$. (ii). $M_2(M(B)) = 200$.
- (iii). $mM_1(M(B)) = 1.58$.
- (iv). $mM_2(M(B)) = 1.378$. (v). $HM_1(M(B)) = 202$.
- (vi). $HM_2(M(B)) = 3085$.
- (vii). $R(M(B)) = 4.4592$ (viii). $\chi(M(B)) = 2.0678$
- (ix) $ISI(M(B)) = 46.1828$.
- (X). $ABC(M(B)) = 16.1203$ (iX) $GAI(M(B)) = 4.9049$
- (X) $SO(M(B)) = 95.876$.

Proof: In $M(B)$, there are two pairs of edges with degrees of end vertices as 1,4 ; 3,4;3,5;3,6;2,5;4,5;4,6 and one edge with degrees of end vertices as 5,4 and 5,6.

With these degree sequences, we can easily get the values.

Theorem 3.3: If $T(B)$ is the Total graph of Bull graph, then

- (i). $M_1(T(B)) = 217$. (ii). $M_2(T(B)) = 425$.
- (iii). $mM_1(T(B)) = 0.85083$.
- (iv). $mM_2(T(B)) = 1.0456$. (v). $HM_1(T(B)) = 13720$.
- (vi) $HM_2(T(B)) = 10881$.
- (vii). $R(T(B)) = 4.324$ (viii). $\chi(T(B)) = 2.0719$
- (ix) $ISI(T(B)) = 150.93$
- (X). $ABC(T(B)) = 18.217$ (iX) $GAI(T(B)) = 9.1821$
- (X) $SO(T(B)) = 122.7$.

Proof: In $M(B)$, there are two pairs of edges with degrees of end vertices as 2,6 ; 2,4; 6,6 and four pairs of edges with degrees of end vertices as 4,6 and 5,6, three pairs of edges with degrees of end vertices as 4,5 and one edge pair with degrees of end vertices as 2,6 and 5,5.

With these degree sequences, we can easily get the values.

Theorem 3.4: If $SD(B)$ is the Total graph of Bull graph, then

$$(i). M_1(SD(B)) = 192. \quad (ii). M_2(SD(B)) = 432.$$

$$(iii). mM_1(SD(B)) = 9.336.$$

$$(iv). mM_2(SD(B)) = 10. \quad (v). HM_1(SD(B))$$

$$= 1.888. \quad (vi) HM_2(SD(B))$$

$$= 6624.$$

$$(vii). R(SD(B)) = 4.386 \quad (viii). \chi(SD(B))$$

$$= 2.133 \quad (ix) ISI(SD(B)) = 43.2$$

$$(X). ABC(SD(B)) = 18.217 \quad (iX) GAI(SD(B))$$

$$= 18.726 \quad (X) SO(SD(B))$$

$$= 142.22.$$

Proof: In shadow graph $SD(B)$, there are eight pairs of edges with degrees of end vertices as 2,6 ; 6,4 and four pairs of edges with degrees of end vertices as 6,6 With these degree sequences, we can easily get the required values.

Conclusion

In this paper we computed first and second Zagreb indices, Randić index, sum-connectivity index, harmonic index, inverse sum indeg index, modified first and second Zagreb indices and first and second hyper Zagreb indices of the Splitting graph of Bull graph.

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